

7 November 2022

Asteroid Transits of the Sun

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Abstract

Asteroid transits across the Sun are predicted for the years 2023 till 2040. None of them can be detected from Earth.

1 Introduction

Transits of the inner planets Mercury and Venus in front of the Sun could be observed several times during the last centuries, see Fig. 1. Accurate measurements of time and position of the shadow cast onto the Sun's disk allowed to determine the astronomical unit - the fundamental length scale of the solar system. The related dimming of the Sun's brightness serves also as a model for transits of extrasolar planets in front of their mother star; as of today this constitutes the most successful method for exoplanet discovery.

Figure 1: Mercury transit on May 9, 2016, recorded by the author (Minor planet Center observatory code K85). Superposition of photos taken every 15 Minutes. Missing mercury shadows are due to clouds.

Asteroid transits of the Sun have not yet been observed from Earth. Such events are rare and difficult to detect due to the small size of the asteroids that can pass in between Earth and Sun. Naturally, the first observation of such a transit would be of interest per se. A measurement of the position of the asteroid's shadow on the solar disk and the local dimming of the Sun's brightness can improve our knowledge of both orbital parameters and the size of the minor planet.

In this paper I present an analysis of asteroid transits till the end of the year 2040. The predictions are based on current asteroid orbital elements and the perturbing effects of the eight planets. The accuracy of these calculations is limited by uncertainties of the asteroid data available as of today, their possible interaction with other minor planets, and numerical imprecisions. Due to these imponderables today an analysis of transits for the years after 2040 would not be meaningful. The dimming effect by the asteroid's shadow can at most be estimated, since the size of many of the smaller asteroids is poorly known.

Obviously, asteroids not yet detected are not considered here. Probably the bigger ones have not been missed in the surveys conducted up to now, so we expect future discoveries of asteroids to reveal only relatively small ones, for which a solar transit can anyway not be observed from

Earth, unless they get really very close.

2 Asteroids that can pass in between Earth and Sun

Only the asteroids of type Aten (semimajor axis below 1 AU and furthest distance from the Sun exceeding 0.983 AU = perihelion Earth orbit) and Apollo (semimajor axis above 1 AU and closest distance from the Sun smaller than 1.017 AU = aphelion Earth orbit) have a chance to transit the Sun, as seen from Earth. This is a relatively small fraction of the more than 1 million known asteroids [1]. The lists provided by the Minor Planet Center [as of September 15, 2022] contain 2350 Aten asteroids [2] and 15109 Apollo asteroids [3], adding up to 17459. Note that this figure is much larger than the number of asteroids discovered till 1988, when M. Hoffmann published a first discussion of asteroid transits [4] based on 54 asteroids, Atens and Apollos.

Of the 17459 minor bodies only a few hundred pass near the line of sight connecting Sun and Earth during the next 20 years, as my analysis shows.

All the Atens and Apollo asteroids for which their size s is known, are smaller than $s_{max} = 10$ km [5, 6]. It seems unlikely that much bigger ones have escaped detection, thus we assume in the following s_{max} as the upper limit on the spatial extension of transiting asteroids.

3 Observability of asteroid transits

With an absolute size s and a distance d from Earth during solar transit, the apparent angular size α of the asteroid's shadow is

$$\alpha/'' = \frac{s/\text{km}}{d/\text{AU}} / 730 \leq \frac{s_{max}/\text{km}}{d/\text{AU}} / 730 = \frac{1}{d/\text{AU}} / 73 \quad (1)$$

Thus only (relatively large!) asteroids with a distance of $d < d_{max} = 0.015$ AU $\approx 2\,000\,000$ km from Earth during transit have a chance of producing a shadow exceeding 1'' in apparant size, which should be observable. For comparison: a Venus transit generates a black circle with a diameter exceeding 50'', Mercury's shadow has a size of 10 – 12'', see Fig. 1. Note: A transit lasts a couple of hours for asteroids closer to the Sun than to Earth during transit, and only a few minutes or even less for asteroids passing near our planet.

Can one detect also fainter dimming effects by observing the Sun during the full duration of the transit? The simple and crude model presented in the following tries to answer this question. The basic idea is to repeat measurements of the dimming effect very often during the transit, and thus gain sensitivity by combining these results. We assume that we know the exact asteroid position, and approximate the FWHM angular resolution of the Earth-based telescope with 1'', including seeing effects. Let's further assume the asteroid does not cross the center of the solar disk (about 1900'' in diameter), but has a smaller apparent track length of typically 1000''. We subdivide the visible solar surface into cells of size of 1'' \times 1'', see Fig. 2. We assume that we make $N = 1000$ independent brightness measurements along the shadow's track, thus two subsequent data points correspond to a movement of the asteroid in front of the solar disk by 1''. The brightness of the cell containing the asteroid at a given moment in time is measured, and compared to the brightness of the neighboring undimmed cells. If the relative precision of a single brightness masurement is $\Delta b_1 = 1\%$, in total a sensitivity of $\Delta b_N = \Delta b_1 / \sqrt{N} = 0.03\%$ can be reached. Consequently an asteroid shadow of angular size $\sqrt{0.03} \cdot 1'' \approx 0.2''$ is detectable, and the above estimate of d_{max} is alleviated to $d_{max} \approx 0.08$ AU. However, this angular size is reachable only if the asteroid is comparatively large! In the following we will therefore focus on asteroid transits with $d \leq 0.1$ AU, since only those have a chance to be observed.

Figure 2: Simple model of solar brightness measurements during asteroid transit. The illustration shows a part of the solar disk, subdivided in cells of 1 arcsecond x 1 arcsecond in size. The shadow represents the transiting asteroid. For explanations see text.

4 Calculation of asteroid transits

Starting point are the orbital elements of the 17459 Atens and Apollo asteroids, as given in the MPCORB.DAT data base by the Minor Planet Center for the epoch 2022-09-08 [7]. In order to predict the orbital elements for a later year, the gravitational effects of the planets need to be taken into account; over a time span of 20 years their perturbing effects can change an asteroid's position by a significant fraction of the angular size of the solar disk. The planetary influences are calculated through a numerical calculation, making use of a Runge-Kutta method to speed it up. The orbital elements of the planets are taken from Ref. [8]. The resulting estimated positional uncertainty for the asteroids is estimated to be below 100'' after 20 years, thus well below the solar disk's radius.

The position of the Sun is calculated using the simple algorithm presented in Ref. [9]. The geocentric equatorial coordinates of Sun and asteroids are calculated for the J2000 equinox. The difference between topocentric and geocentric coordinates is negligible for minor planets more than 0.1 AU away from Earth, and the condition of a transit is fulfilled if for a certain time the angular difference β between center of Sun and asteroid is below $\beta_{max} = 0.26^\circ = 950''$, which is the angular radius of the solar disk. For smaller distances the difference geocentric-topocentric matters and the value of β_{max} - used to define and identify solar transits - is enlarged to take into account different possible observer positions on Earth.

To search for transits the predicted asteroid positions are compared to the Sun's position as a function of time, in steps of 10 seconds. For nearby and thus very fast transits the step size is reduced to 1 second.

5 Results

In total 762 asteroids are identified that get near the center of the sun, as seen from Earth, within $\beta < 0.5^\circ$, for the time span January 1, 2023 till December 31, 2040. Only a fraction of them will actually transit the sun, and only very few of those get close to Earth at this moment.

The following table lists asteroids that are predicted to transit in front of the solar disk ($\beta \leq \beta_{max} = 0.26^\circ$), with a distance $d \leq 0.1$ AU. The time given in the table corresponds to the

designation	date and hour (UT)	Sun RA	Sun DEC	ang. dist. β in deg.	dist. d in AU
2020 SF4	2027-8-15 14:13	$9^h 38^m$	$14^0 7'$	0.21	0.089
2012 CS46	2028-4-16 14:45	$1^h 39^m$	$10^0 19'$	0.12	0.096

Table 1: Asteroid transits for close distance d Earth-asteroid ≤ 0.1 AU during the years 2023 till 2040. The given geocentric equatorial coordinates right ascension (RA) and declination (DEC) of the center of the Sun refer to the J2000 equinox. The time corresponds to the smallest separation β from the solar disk's center. The angular distance refers to the line of sight between the centers of Earth and Sun.

smallest apparent angular distance β . For this moment the position of the sun is given, but not the asteroid's equatorial coordinates, since they are subject to uncertainties in the calculation and depend on the position of the observer on earth. Note that due to the limited precision of currently available orbital elements and/or numerical inaccuracies in the simulation, both transit time and right ascension and declination of the asteroid might deviate from the exact time and positional coordinates. However, even if the predicted time is not correct, the transit might still happen, some minutes or hours earlier or later.

The size of Apollo asteroid 2020 SF4 is not known, however absolute brightness measurements (26.2 mag) indicate that it is certainly less than 100 m in size [10]. Also 2012 CS46 is an asteroid of type Apollo, and again the brightness data favor a small asteroid [10]. Thus both transits as listed in Table 1 will not be detectable from Earth.

6 Conclusions

Based on the current knowledge about asteroids and their orbital elements transits across the Sun are predicted for the years 2023 till 2040. In spite of the large number of asteroids in our solar system, none of those transits is likely to be detectable from Earth. The main reasons are the large fraction of minor planets always orbiting outside of Earth's orbit, and the small size of most asteroids.

References

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